

MAELSTROM

Smart technology for MARinE Litter SusTainable
RemOval and Management

D5.2

Final report on operation of
the Seabed Cleaning
System in Venice

10/03/2025

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Executive Summary

The MAELSTROM project aims to test and evaluate innovative technologies for the removal of marine litter in different coastal environments, also assessing their impact on the ecosystems in chosen demo sites and evaluating the economic and societal benefits of the MAELSTROM solutions within local economies. This deliverable illustrates the tests and cleaning campaigns carried out in 2022 and 2023 with the Seabed Cleaning Campaigns in the Venice Coastal area. The system was demonstrated to be quick and efficient, to be able to operate up to 20 m of depth and to collect items up to 130kg, having a real time control on the deck of all the operations of the cable robot, reaching TRL7. Although visibility made the Venice Coastal area an extreme scenario for the implementation of the Seabed Cleaning Platform, during the tests the Platform managed to efficiently and selectively collect more than 2200 kg of seafloor litter, and the technology was publicly demonstrated to the Venice stakeholders and citizen in June 2023. The collected litter was then used for the testing of the AI driven Sorting Robot and for the recycling processes of the platform. In the last part of the deliverable, we list the lesson learnt and suggestions for further upgrading of the Seabed Cleaning Platform to reach TRL9.

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1 Introduction to the MAELSTROM project

MAELSTROM is a four-year project Funded by the European Commission under the H2020 Programme - Topic CE-FNR-09-2020 Pilot action for the removal of marine plastics and litter. The project compiles a consortium of 14 international partners led by the Institute of Marine Sciences of the Italian National Research Council (CNR). The project partners span academia and industry, using the expertise of research institutes, enterprises, and NGOs from 8 European countries. MAELSTROM's main goal is to reduce the impacts of marine litter (ML) in coastal ecosystems by identifying accumulation hotspots and removing the existing litter from the coastal seabed and the water column of rivers before it reaches the sea. This action is supported and enacted through a thorough circular economy and societal-oriented solution. In particular, the project (i) sets out a reliable multidisciplinary and scientifically sound approach for the assessment of marine debris distribution and impact on marine life in highly valuable ecosystems and protected areas; (ii) designs and manufactures scalable, replicable, and automated technologies, co-powered with renewable energy and second generation fuel, to identify, remove and sort ML; (iii) evaluates over time the effectiveness of ML removal devices along with their impact on local ecosystems; (iv) integrates different technologies to track, sort, and recycle all types of collected ML into valuable raw materials for future marketization; (v) assesses the economic and societal impact of the MAELSTROM solutions providing also a comprehensive life-cycle assessment of the technologies and products; (vi) enhances social awareness about the ML issue and engages citizens and stakeholders in MAELSTROM activities; (vii) interplays with similar projects to maximize innovation uptake for ML removal within and outside the EU.

The project is implementing two innovative and environmentally sustainable technologies to achieve this goal. These technologies consist of a Bubble Barrier to intercept floating and sub-surface litter on rivers before they enter the oceans, powered by sustainable energy derived from innovative floating photovoltaic panels, and a completely new solution for the removal of small and large items from the seabed in the form of a Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform, already successfully tested in the Venice coastal area (<https://www.maelstrom-h2020.eu/maelstrom->

[outputs/#technologies](#)). An AI-driven robot is used to identify and segregate plastics collected from the coastal environment, and three new processes have been used to recycle the retrieved organic and plastic litter. These are transformed into higher-value materials whose characteristics, performance, and economic value are assessed for future marketization. The project focuses on the involvement of the local, national, and international stakeholders, paving the way to the long-term adoption of the technologies by the local stakeholders in the pilot areas. MAELSTROM carries out several actions to enhance ocean literacy and community engagement. Frequent public clean-up events situated on beaches in Portugal, Spain, and Italy have provided an engagement and education platform for citizens to improve awareness around the issues of ML and the tools used in addressing the problem. The project team has also organized public demonstrations of the ML removal technologies at several national, European, and international scientific conferences and High-Level meetings. The public demonstration and launch of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in the Venice lagoon took place in June 2023, and the launch of the Bubble Barrier in the Porto region will take place in October 2023. These activities involve, inform, and inspire citizens across Europe. The project has delivered webinars and a freely available newsletter designed to communicate both the problems and solutions of ML pollution to a wider audience.

Stakeholders have been involved from the beginning of the project as core actors, each with particular and dedicated levels of communication and involvement. Actors such as environment management entities; waste management and remediation companies; local enterprises and commercial entities; local, regional and national governments; industry partners; civil society; and local schools and community groups, have been closely collaborated with in the design, coordination, and implementation of the project, demonstrating enthusiasm and support for MAELSTROM's contribution to the ML problem. Local management entities such as those in Vila do Conde, Portugal and the Venice municipality, Italy, have been involved from early stages as core stakeholders for the co-design and co-implementation of the ML removal technologies.

2 MAELSTROM Consortium

The MAELSTROM project consortium consists of:

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2.1 Aim and scope of the Deliverable

This Deliverable 5.2 "Final report on operation of the Seabed Cleaning System in Venice" contains the work carried out in task T5.2 Seafloor/water column removal implementation: Venice coastal area, Italy corresponding to WP5 ML Removal in Selected Demonstration Sites of the MAELSTROM project, focusing on the application of remediation technologies deployed at demo sites in the Venice Lagoon/coast and the Ave River estuary in the Porto Region.

The aim of this work was to provide documentation and results about the demonstration activities of the MAELSTROM automated Seabed Cleaning technology in the selected locations within the Venice demo site.

The Seabed Cleaning Platform based on cable robotics, developed and installed in Venice during WP3 and WP5-T5.1, was tested at two pilot areas in Venice: Sacca Fisola, close to the city of Venice in the Venice Lagoon and an abandoned mussel farm in the Venice coastal area at sea, fully described in WP2- D2.3. The scope was to put at hard test and therefore improve the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in the attempt to remove historically accumulated litter and to adequately feed the circular economy chain established and operating in MAELSTROM project, including the marine litter smart identification and segregation systems.

The initial idea was to operate the Seabed Cleaning Platform based on Cable Robotics according to an alternating operational scheme. It was planned to do the cleaning of the same area in parcels of about 25m x 25m each, 4 times along 3 years. However, the partners have decided to concentrate the cleaning campaigns in 2 times, covering larger areas, due to the need to assemble and disassemble the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform each time it was used.

The main reasons for that are the high costs of renting and transport the modular pontoons for sea utilization in coastal area, where all the equipment was installed in and the high costs of assembling, disassembling and fine tune each time all the equipment of the whole Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform.

2.1 The Seabed Cleaning platform team

The team that implemented the Seabed Cleaning Platform was composed by ST-Servizi Tecnici, TECNALIA, CNRS- LIRMM:

ST – Servizi Tecnici was the responsible of moving the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform from the Arsenale to Sacca Fisola and from spot to spot during the cleaning. Their strong know-how about the Venice Lagoon, and about naval engineering and sailing contributed significantly to the success of the cleaning campaigns. ST was the responsible of the set-up of the industrial equipment and supervised the whole set-up of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform.

TECNALIA was responsible of the set-up and validation of the cable robot from the mechanical, electrical and control point of view. The main contribution of TECNALIA was their expertise in cable robotics. They developed the software to control the parameters of the cable robot and monitoring the cable tension.

TECNALIA participated actively during the whole cleaning campaign, with a team of four people experts in robotics. They were responsible of controlling the cable robot from the radio-controller and the responsible of removing the marine litter from the seabed.

TECNALIA and ST-Servizi Tecnici were the responsible of the control system of the fully operational mobile platform and for assembly and disassembly of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform and all equipment once the cleaning campaign finished.

Figure 1 - Software of HMI developed by TECNALIA to control the cable robot and to monitor in real time the cable tension of the cable robot.

Figure 2 - Expert in robotics from TECNALIA team controlling the cable robot with the radio-controller during the removing of ML at Sacca-Fisola.

CNRS-LIRMM was responsible for developing and adjusting the mapping/navigation software and its Graphic User Interface. This software collects, synchronizes, records, and displays all the data from the underwater sensors, and from the cable robot. Based on the RTK GPS measurements, it also makes the frames' conversions to compute the geographic coordinates of the positions of every depth measurement made by the DVL beams. These bathymetric data are stored in a georeferenced 100 m x 100 m wide map (this size can be changed if needed). The local depth map, under the robot, is computed and updated from the georeferenced map after each GPS measurement and it is displayed in the GUI to provide an easy interpretable view of the bathymetry. This

map also prevents the robot from colliding with the bottom. The user can also click on the map to automatically navigate to a desired position, where waste is located wherever the visibility of the water allows it.

The GUI software is also able to generate exploration trajectories to perform the mapping of the site when this latter is visited for the first time. Then the robot “scans” the area with the DVL and the data from the DVL are filtered to remove the acoustic outliers. In fact, occasional erroneous measurements occur because of the multiple acoustic paths between the DVL, the seabed and the sea surface. This filtering was also tested and improved during the first cleaning campaign. Furthermore, the software also estimates the tide level in real time, without requiring any data from a shore tidal station.

Figure 3 - A screenshot of the Graphic User Interface (GUI) of the mapping and navigation software, tested and improved in Venice. On the left, one can see the bathymetric map, in the middle, the data from the sensors, and on the right, the video from the smart camera displayed in real time.

2.2 The Seabed Cleaning Platform Installation

The Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform was installed and set-up in Porto Marghera during July 2022. As the depth in Porto Marghera was around 2 m and for safety

reasons, the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform was moved to the Arsenale for the first trials and spent there the summertime.

In September 2022, ST-Servizi Tecnici, TECNALIA and CNRS-LIRMM executed the pending points listed in D5.1 to finish the installation of Seabed Cleaning Platform based on cable robotics:

- Aspiration system was modified and set-up for the cleaning tests.
- The industrial crane and the underwater basket for depositing the removed marine litter were installed in the floating platform.
- The visibility in Sacca Fisola was much worse than expected; the visibility was around 20-25 cm whereas the vision cameras were at 52 cm from the lower area of the gripper. To tackle this problem, TECNALIA bought articulated arms and fixed the vision cameras to them to set the camera closer to the gripping position. Moreover, TECNALIA developed an underwater image enhancement software to increase the capability of the pilot to identify objects. This image enhancement software was critical to perform the two cleaning campaigns.

Figure 4. Very poor visibility in Sacca Fisola.

Figure 5 - Improved vision for the cable robot: Articulated arms mounted on the underwater robotic platform to get closer the vision cameras to the marine litter; b) real time image enhancement software developed by TECNALIA to cope with the poor visibility in Sacca Fisola.

All the equipment of the Seabed Cleaning platform is described in detail in Appendix 1.

2.3 The first cleaning campaign

The first cleaning campaign took place from 12 to 30th September 2022; the cleaning site was Sacca Fisola and the area covered was aprox 120 x 30 m. The main participants of this cleaning campaign were: TECNALIA, ST- Servizi Tecnici and CNRS-LIRMM. They had the support of CNR.

The list of activities and the time needed is shown below:

ACTIVITY	DATES
Finish the set-up of whole equipment of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform at Arsenale	12- 14th September 2022
Move the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform to Sacca Fisola	15th September 2022 (morning)
Start the cleaning campaign at Sacca Fisola	15th September 2022 (afternoon)
Finish the cleaning campaign at Sacca Fisola	28th September 2022
Move the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform to Porto Marghera	29th September 2022
Disassembly the whole Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform and the floating platform	From 29th September 2022 to 7th October

The following video shows the steps given during the first cleaning campaign.
#Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform – Removing Marine Litter from Venice Lagoon (Maelstrom Project) - YouTube

Figure 6 - First cleaning Campaign: Sacca Fisola – Venice.

Figure 7 - The Seabed Cleaning Platform based on cable robotics in Sacca Fisola during the first cleaning campaign.

Figure 8 - Green spots indicate the points where marine litter were removed.

Figure 9 - Bathymetry map of Sacca Fisola provided by CNR.

Let us briefly summarize the litter removal process during the cleaning campaigns with the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform. First, a location is selected with the help of the bathymetry provided by CNR. The objective is to find a zone where big litter items can be seen on the bathymetry, and to move the floating barge to the corresponding GPS coordinates, following georeferenced multibeam maps of the seabed previously loaded on the navigation system.

As soon as the barge arrived at the desired location and properly moored with 2 hydraulic operated spuds in shallow water, a scan is performed with the DVL at sea level. The scan gives an accurate mapping of the zone, offering a reliable and real-time updated feedback to the operator. Once the scan is done, the robot can move freely within its safe working zone, as every dangerous object (i.e. large objects that could collide with the robot) are detected and projected on the Graphical User Interface (GUI) depth map. A second underwater DVL scan is then performed closer to the seabed, using the prior scan to move close but above the seabed, allowing

for better resolution mapping, but also for more visibility on the potentially lying litter. While the robot is scanning the zone for the second time, the operator can click on the image (within the GUI) to identify macro litter. Each time the operator clicks on the image, the depth (given by the depth map) and the 2D coordinates of the clicked pixel are saved. Finally, once this last scan is completed, the robot can automatically move a few centimeters above the saved coordinates, giving a complete view of the object and letting the operator grab or suck the macro litter. The grabbed object can then be retrieved on the barge, and the robot can automatically move to the next litter lying on the seabed. All the software components needed to perform this removal process have been developed (in WP3) and tested in real conditions and improved in the framework of WP5.

Figure 10 - Identification of the coordinates and items removed during the first cleaning campaign (TECNALIA team).

Figure 11 - Colleagues from TECNALIA and CNRS-LIRMM working in the control room during the cleaning campaign.

During the cleaning campaign the DVL embarked on the underwater robot platform broke, and therefore, CNRS-LIRMM and TECNALIA had to rely on bathymetry only. So, for more convenience, CNRS-LIRMM added the bathymetry map within the GUI. They centered the bathymetry on the robot's end effector coordinates and cropped the image to a 28x28m square. They chose the width so the platform's pool will always be in the cropped zone, regardless of the platform's orientation or the robot's end effector position. They added a scaled cross in the center of the square, which always represents the robot's end effector. Then, they overlaid the platform's pool on the bathymetry square so the pilot could have continuous information on the robot's position. They also added a red rectangle, which represents the working and safe zone of the robot, to prevent any collision between the platform and the robot's cables. They added a red and green dot representing the platform's port and the starboard GPSs, respectively. Then, they rotated the bathymetry square, considering the platform's course and the robot's system coordinates, as shown below. This rotation allowed the pilot to control the robot easily and, thus, reach the target much quicker. For convenience, they added a 6x6m zoom of the bathymetry square, allowing the pilot to see the target more clearly.

Moving the platform to a specific target was difficult and time-consuming, so CNRS-LIRMM connected a laptop to the network and put it on the boat. They displayed a 50x50m bathymetry square centered on the platform on the screen's laptop and added a red cross on the target, as shown below. Thanks to this real-time interface, the boat's pilot could see the platform moving as he drove. Then, the objective was to move the platform, so the target lay within the robot's workspace (the red rectangle).

Figure 12 - Improvement of the Graphic User Interface (GUI) of the mapping and navigation software, tested and improved in Venice (CNRS-LIRMM) and PC added on the boat (with geo-referenced target and platform) to help the pilot to move the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform from spot to spot. Colleagues of ST and CNRS-LIRMM mounted on the boat that moved the whole Seabed Cleaning Platform.

Figure 13 - Tyre removed by the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform during the first cleaning campaign

Figure 14 - Marine Litter (bed frame) removed by the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform during the first cleaning campaign

Figure 15 - The team: TECNALIA, ST-Servizi Tecnici and CNRS-LIRMM in Sacca Fisola during the first cleaning campaign

The following images show the different types of marine litter removed during the first cleaning campaign at Sacca Fisola.

Example of ML removed from Sacca Fisola during final testing of the robot

Example of ML removed from Sacca Fisola during final testing of the robot

2 large Wood+metal structure

Part of machine in Steel Truck tire

Plastic materials and others

Figure 16 - Examples of marine litter removed in Sacca Fisola during the first cleaning campaign.

Table 1 – ML removed from the Sacca Fisola site in 2022.

Type of material	Litter	Total Number
Glass	Fragments	55
	Bottles	11
Plastic	Videotape	1
	Bottles	1
	Medical blister	1
	Straw	1
	Packaging fragments	48
	Clamp	1
	Fragments	19
	Foam pieces	2
	Cable	1
	Band	1
	Label	1
Metal	Net	1
	Cans	10
	Gripper	1
	Fragments	8
Mixed	Plug	1
	Cover	1
	Pedalo	1
	Hanger	1

Ceramic	Pottery fragments	6
Organic	Bone	1
Fabric	Tissue pieces	2

Once the cleaning campaign at Sacca Fisola was finished, TECNALIA and ST-Servizi Tecnici disassembled the whole Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform including the floating platform. All the equipment, except the control, electronics and the underwater sensors, was kept in Venice at ST facilities until the next cleaning campaign.

Figure 17 - Disassembly of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform at Porto Marghera after the first cleaning campaign.

The litter collected in the cleaning campaign was tracked with the MAELSTROM app to include them in the sorting and recycling process. In

Figure 18 - Example of the tracking of the ML collected in Sacca Fisola in 2022 (1820 kg of litter collected) to the recycling.

The flow of the collected litter to recycling: a total of 1820 kg of ML was collected. Some material was sent to specific authorized plants (i.e. Ecopneus for tyres, PR EcologyWH for metals, etc.) as required by the Italian waste legislation. A total of 1255 kg of litter was given to GEES, that mechanically recycled part of the litter and distributed the rest to the different partner for sorting and other recycling processes.

Figure 18 - Example of the tracking of the ML collected in Sacca Fisola in 2022 (1820 kg of litter collected) to the recycling.

2.4 Lesson learnt during the first cleaning campaign at Sacca Fisola

- Seabed cleaning platform with the underwater cable robot worked well.
- Underwater cable robot worked well; its operability is very good. The robot is fast and can pick marine litter up to 130 kg. The movement is smooth and accurate, high rotation capability, great maneuverability. The robot frame was out of the water for assembling/mounting and maintenance operations and for safely translating the floating barge from spot to spot (parking position) and also having the robot inside the water for marine litter removal operations (working position).
- Anchoring system (Mooring system with hydraulic spuds) of the seabed cleaning platform to the seabed worked very well, the system is very fast and stable and has been used even for precision positioning tests with the help of Differential GPS (DGPS) present on board.
- Whole system was tested until 5 m depth.

- Positioning of the cleaning platform using RTK-GPS and the bathymetry maps of CNR worked very well: the position of the robot is indicated on the bathymetric map of the seabed, where the position of the waste items is also depicted. The robot moves in manual mode with a joystick.
- Computation in real time the geographic position of the robot, thanks to Real Time Kinematic (RTK) GPS and to several Inertial Measurement Units - devices which measure and report the position and orientation.
- PC was added on the boat (with geo-referenced target and platform) to help the pilot to move the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform from spot to spot. Very good idea that allowed to reduce the time to move from one spot to the next one with the tug-boat.
- Visibility nearly null, this was the major breakthrough; partially solved with the real time enhancement software and the addition of articulated arms to locate the vision cameras closer to the sea
- Lights embarked on the underwater robot platform were not useful at Sacca Fisola due the poor visibility of the water
- Most of the large marine litter was partially sunk on the mud; whereas small & medium size litter were completely sunk on the mud; we were able to identify/see them after cleaning "the ball of mud" with water jets.

Figure 19 - Ball of mud directly removed from the seabed in Sacca Fisola and example of litter found once cleaned.

- Suction device (free pass of 140 mm) couldn't be used in these conditions (at least in Sacca Fisola)

- VDL embarked on the robot frame damaged, no bathymetry maps on real time could be used; partners trusted on the bathymetry maps provided by CNR
- Main gripper was a bit small; a bigger gripper would have made easier the picking of the tyres
- Floating platform was only able to work with waves of max (+/- 0,25 m)
- Cleaning times:
 - Time to move from one spot to the next one with the tug-boat – quick fast (aprox 5-10 min)
 - Time to reach the seabed with the robot – very fast (seconds)
 - Time to localize and identify the marine litter using the cameras and onboard sensors: due to the poor visibility this task is highly time consuming.
 - Time to approximate the removal tool to the target object. Very fast (seconds)
 - Time to grasp object and move to the collecting basket: several minutes because the main gripper is too small, the tire is likely to slip off the fingers; good orientation of the gripper with the tyre was needed.

2.5 The second cleaning campaign

The second cleaning campaign took place from 22nd May to 14th June 2023. The cleaning sites were the Abandoned Mussel Farm and Sacca Fisola. The main participants of this cleaning campaign were ST-Servizi Tecnici, TECNALIA, CNRS-LIRMM and CNR.

The list of activities and the time needed is shown below:

ACTIVITY	DATES
ST performed the maintenance operations of the industrial equipment and the cable robot; they made the assembly of the pontoons and fixed the 4 metallic posts and the control room in the floating platform; they	Before 22 nd May 2023

also installed most of the industrial equipment on the pontoons. Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform at Porto Marghera.	
TECNALIA carried the mechanical and electrical assembly and set-up of the cable robot and the electronics embarked on the underwater robot mobile platform. ST finished the installation and set-up of the gripper and the aspiration system; solved some mechanical and electrical/digital problems in the gripper and finalized a remote control unit of all equipment that worked with local commands and remotely through the main control cabinet . Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform at Porto Marghera	22 – 26th May 2023
CNRS-LIRMM and TECNALIA connected and made the set-up of all the sensors onboard. The new VDL was installed and CNRS-LIRMM improved the Graphical User Interface and generated real-time bathymetry maps with it. All the equipment was prepared to perform the cleaning. Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform at Porto Marghera; the initial idea was to start the cleaning at the Abandoned Mussel Farm but was not possible	29-31 st May 2023
ST moved the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform to Sacca Fisola. Second Cleaning at Sacca Fisola	1-2 nd June 2023
ST managed the translation of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform to Punta Sabbioni; first validations at 17 m-depths with sea currents up to 0.6 m/sec !!! (much higher than the ones used for the design of the cable robot)	5 th June 2023
Cleaning at Abandoned Mussel Farm. All the Boys and ropes in the selected area were removed with Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform. Once finished the cleaning campaign the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform was moved to Porto Marghera.	6-7 th June 2023
Works at Porto Marghera and preparation of the “Live demonstration of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform”	8 th June 2023
“Live demonstration of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform” in Punta della Dogana	9 th June 2023
Disassembly the whole Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform and the floating platform	from 12 th June to 19 th June

The role and contribution of **TECNALIA**, **CNRS-LIRMM** and **ST – Servizi Tecnici** was the same as they had during the first cleaning campaign.

CNR and **ST – Servizi Tecnici** coordinated the cleaning campaign at the Abandoned Mussel Farm. **CNR** was also responsible of monitoring the marine litter collected during the cleaning campaign. **CNR** measured the sea currents along the water column all the time spent at Abandoned Mussel Farm.

At Sacca Fisola, the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform was georeferenced in the last bathymetry map provided by **CNR**. A new DVL was installed as a substitution for the broken one (managed by **TECNALIA**). **CNRS-LIRMM** improved the Graphical User Interface and generated real-time bathymetry maps with it. All the equipment

was prepared to perform the cleaning. TECNALIA improved the underwater image enhancement software to increase the capability of the pilot to identify objects.

Figure 20 - Photos taken in Sacca Fisola during the second cleaning campaign.

First validation test at 17 m depth with high sea currents

In a location close to Punta Sabbioni, the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform was tested at 17 m-depths with sea currents up to 0.6 m/sec !!! . Note that the cable robot was designed to support sea currents of 0.2 m/sec at 20m depth and of 0.6 m/sec at surface level. Therefore, we can conclude that the underwater cable robot is stable at high depths under severe sea currents.

Table 2- Design criteria: Sea currents to be supported by the cable robot at 17 m depth (see at D3.1)

Max speed of sea current at	[m/s]
Surface level	0,6
3 m depth	0,3
20 m depth	0,2

Figure 21- Red Point 1: location of the first validation tests at 17m-depth with sea currents until 0.6 m/sec; Red Point 2: mooring area of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform in Punta Sabbioni.

Cleaning campaign at the Abandoned Mussel Farm

Figure 22 – Location and Bathymetry map of the abandoned mussel farm and zoom on the area to be cleaned.

Photos of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform as shown below:

Figure 23 - Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform at the Abandoned Mussel Farm.

Figure 24 - Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform at the Abandoned Mussel Farm: removing of ropes and boys.

The seabed in the area of the Abandoned Mussel Farm is quite flat with depths around 14-15 m.

The Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform was georeferenced in the bathymetry map provided by CNR. The bathymetry map was precise and identified very well the location of the ropes and buoys to be removed.

The Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform was fixed to four mooring blocks previously arranged by CNR and ST – Servizi Tecnici. The translation of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform from spot to spot was done manually by adjusting the length of the ropes fixed to the mooring blocks and with the support of a small boat. Once fixed to the four mooring blocks, the stability of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform was good.

The sea currents were measured in real time with an ADCP by CNR, with the aim of performing the cleaning with the conditions estimated in the design phase. During the cleaning, the sea currents were in the range desired:

- at surface level and during the first 5 m of Depth: 0.3 m/s
- depther aprox 0.15 m/s
- at nearly -14.8 m, sea current at aprox 0.1 m/s

The visibility of the water is very good; it seems there are 2 layers, upper one on the surface with very good visibility, full of fresh water coming from the river (we were

nearly in front the Sile river mouth) with sea currents around 0.3 m/s and a second one, closer to the seabed, with sea current much lower but with worse visibility. Under these water conditions, the effect of the underwater lights was visible and helped the operator of the robot in the removal operation of the marine litter.

Figure 25 - Effect of the underwater lights in Abandoned Mussel Farm

TECNALIA improved the real time image enhancement software, and the updated version worked better than in the previous cleaning, in both cleaning sites.

Figure 26 - Real time image enhancement software developed by TECNALIA.

Figure 27 - Cleaning the platform at the arrival after sea trials.

Figure 28 - The team: CNR, ST-Servizi Tecnici, TECNALIA and CNRS-LIRMM in the Abandoned Mussel Farm during the second cleaning campaign.

2023

- Tyres
- Ropes
- Nets
- Wood
- Construction waste
- Machine parts
- Steel cables
- Buoys and large plastic objects
- Glass bottles...

Figure 29 - Marine litter removed during the second cleaning campaign.

2.5 The Seabed Cleaning Platform cleaning results

Seabed cleaning operation – Abandoned Mussel Farm

The cleaning operations carried out at the Abandoned Mussel Farm yielded significant results, both in terms of the length of ropes removed and the total number of objects successfully collected.

The operations on 6 and 7 June 2023 removed mussel farm waste, ropes and buoys. On 6 June, the first operation successfully removed an entire rope, while the second operation involved cutting and extracting another rope to ensure its complete removal. On 7 June, the first operation removed a single rope, while the second focused on an assembly of ropes and a 125 x 61 cm buoy. With the help of the Venice State Police Diving Unit, it was also possible to remove two other buoys floating in the water column, identified thanks to the MBES.

Figure 30 - Images of the mussel farm clean-up using the robotic marine debris removal platform: a. Real-time monitoring of the seabed with identification of debris such as ropes and nets; b. Use of the robotic platform to recover debris from the seabed; c. Recovery of ropes and aquaculture equipment, including a float; d. Removal of a plastic buoy covered with marine debris.

Although four ropes were removed, the post-cleaning MBES mapping showed the presence of three ropes instead of the expected two. This discrepancy can be explained by the fact that one of the ropes was partially cut off during removal,

leaving a small part on the seafloor. Furthermore, although there are four removal points corresponding to the harvested tops, their positions on the map do not coincide with the original ones. This is because the divers bundled the ropes together during the operations to facilitate their removal from the platform.

Figure 31 - The images show the cleaning and removal of marine litter at the Mussel Farm. In the first map (a), landmarks (buoys and removal points) and underwater ropes routes are highlighted. The second map (b.) shows a visualisation of the same information, but for post-cleanup operations. The area outlined in black indicates the specific intervention area.

Within the sub-area where the seabed cleaning platform operated (6715 m²), the ropes present were reduced from an initial length of 404 metres in 2022 to 126 metres in 2023, representing a removal rate of 69%. Including an additional segment of cable removed outside the sub-area, the total initial cable length increases to 514 metres, which was reduced to 129 metres, resulting in an **effective removal rate of 75%**. These lengths were calculated by integrating bathymetric data with the length calculation tools in ArcGIS Pro.

In terms of object removal, the total number of items decreased from 9 (3 buoys and 6 ropes) to 3 ropes, as all buoys were successfully removed. This equates to an overall removal rate of 67%, leaving only 33% of the original objects in the area. These results highlight the effectiveness of the clean-up operations and underscore the importance of targeted interventions in addressing marine debris accumulation.

Chemical analysis of the collected ropes identified the material as polyamide 6 (PA6), also known as nylon. This semi-crystalline polymer is robust, has excellent

abrasion and chemical resistance, and a density of 1.14 g/cm^3 . The total weight of the collected ropes was $260 \text{ kg} (\pm 10 \text{ kg})$.

Bathymetric data analysis further revealed that the total length of ropes within, and in part outside, the operational area was 514 metres. Assuming a diameter of 2.5 cm, the estimated mass of the ropes based on the MBES data corresponded to approximately 287 kg, aligning closely with the measured weight of the collected ropes. These results demonstrate that multibeam data are not only effective for accurately georeferencing objects on the seabed but also valuable for estimating their physical characteristics, such as weight and size.

Seabed cleaning operation – Sacca Fisola

During the first clean-up campaign in Sacca Fisola, conducted between 15 and 27 September 2022, a significant number of marine debris of various types was collected. Among the items recovered were a wooden panel, a rope, a coiled steel cable, several bricks, a plastic net, a steel bar, a trolley, part of a steel wagon, glass bottles, a Venetian cart, twelve truck tyres, a five-metre-long aluminium roof panel, and a steel roll bar. Other materials included plastic sheets, textile, numerous plastic fragments, aluminium cans, an electronic circuit board, a steel and concrete block, wood, electric cables, and steel frames (Figure 32).

Figure 32 - Images of marine waste recovery operations during the Sacca Fisola clean-up campaigns: a. Recovery of a piece of steel machinery; b. Removal of a tyre; c. Removal of a 5-metre-long aluminium cover panel; d. Mixed waste collected, including plastic fragments, aluminium cans and an electronic circuit board. These pictures highlight the variety of materials recovered.

During the second cleaning campaign, conducted on 1 and 2 June 2023, the robotic platform employed its grab bucket to collect marine litter in four specific locations within the designated cleaning area at Sacca Fisola. A total of 197 objects were removed, including items such as glass, plastic, metal, and mixed materials (Table 3).

Table 3- ML that was removed from the Sacca Fisola site in 2023.

TYPE OF MATERIAL	LITTER	TOTAL	
Glass	Bottle	4	
	Fragments	88	
Plastic	Bag	4	
	Blister	2	
	Bottle	2	
	Cable	3	
	Fork	1	
	Fragments	15	
	Gasket	2	
	Lable	3	
	Packaging	14	
	Pipe	1	
	Rope	1	
	Sanitary	1	
	Seal	1	
	Shoe heel	1	
	Spoon	1	
	Tape	1	
	Tire	1	
	Tumbler	1	
	Metal	Can	2
		Coil	2
Copper wire		1	
Ironing board		1	
Metal plate		1	
Piece of can		1	
Piece of metal		6	
Piece of radiator		1	
Pipe		2	
Sheet metal		2	
Mixed material	Battery component	1	
	Electric wire	1	
	Shoe	1	
Building material	Building material	19	
	Clay	1	
Wood	Briccola	1	
Fabric	Fragments	7	

The use of the grab bucket allowed for the efficient collection of larger objects and fragments that were distributed across the cleaning area. Some items, such as metal fragments or small pieces of plastic, were not easily detectable with the MBES but were successfully located and removed thanks to the platform's direct intervention.

To assess the effectiveness of the Robotic Seabed Cleaning Platform, the presence of macro-litter on the seafloor before and after the cleaning campaigns was mapped through high resolution multibeam echosounders. As well, video

inspections with a camera were carried out by divers, mini ROV and by the robotic platform cameras to ground truth the interpretation of the targets identified with the multibeam data. Methodological details are reported in deliverable D2.3 and D2.4. The seafloor macro-litter distribution of the Sacca Fisola area was assessed through MBES high resolution mapping in four surveys May 2022, November 2022, May 2023 and December 2023.

In the cleaned area in Sacca Fisola, a total of 126 seafloor items were counted in May 2022, while in November 2022 (after the cleaning) only 51 seafloor items were mapped. The comparison between the two maps clearly shows the disappearance of the items removed by the Seabed Cleaning Platform (Figure 33 - Map of the area selected for the cleaning operations in May 2022 (up-before cleaning) and November 2022 (down-post cleaning)). Since the cleanup covered a total area of about 0.02 km², the density of seafloor items per km² in the rectangle is about 6322 items/km² in May 2022 and 2558 items/km² in 2022, showing a substantial improvement in the cleaned area with a **59% reduction of the detected items**.

This value reflects the ability of the robotic platform to tackle marine litter effectively, while also highlighting the challenges posed in the heavily anthropized environment of Sacca Fisola. The proximity of a municipal waste collection point contributes significantly to the continuous accumulation of debris in the lagoon and the intense boat traffic contributes to sediment resuspension also due to propellers ploughing the channel seafloor, as shown in Figure 33 - bottom left zoom. In this area, the cable robot could rely almost only to the bathymetric data: the cable robot cameras were under performing due to high water turbidity and low visibility.

Figure 33 - Map of the area selected for the cleaning operations in May 2022 (up-before cleaning) and November 2022 (down-post cleaning).

A comparative temporal analysis between the data from 2022 and 2023 revealed significant dynamics, including the displacement of debris due to currents or nautical activities and the disappearance of other objects following the cleaning

operations (Figure 33). These findings underline both the complexity of the seafloor marine litter problem and the effectiveness of repeated clean-up efforts in mitigating its impact.

2.6 Public demonstration in the Grand Canal

The technology was demonstrated in a public event in the Grand Canal at Punta della Dogana on June 9, 2023, involving the Municipality of Venice, the local stakeholders and the general public. The participants were able to visit the platform and see the operations of the robot.

Figure 34 - Public event at the Punta della Dogana in Venice on June 9, 2023

2.7 Lesson learnt and possible improvements and upgrade of the platform to TRL9

The cleaning campaign carried out in the Venice Lagoon near Sacca Fisola Island and at the Abandoned Mussel Farm in the northern Adriatic Sea coastal area, in front of the Sile River outlet, demonstrated the readiness of all equipment installed

on the modular platform and its capability to operate efficiently in these two distinct environments.

However, during the second cleaning campaign, some issues arose related to the navigation and the availability of a tugboat to transport the Seabed Cleaning Platform for the operations at sea.

Therefore, to achieve a general upgrade of the naval characteristics—such as speed, fuel consumption, deck space, and maneuverability—a redesign of the hull shape (modular elements on a monohull structure) is recommended.

The modular platform's square-shaped hull, including the bow and stern sections, results in suboptimal navigational performance. Therefore, a redesign incorporating properly faired bow and stern elements is recommended to enhance hydrodynamic efficiency.

In naval architecture, the hull's shape significantly influences a vessel's performance, including speed, fuel consumption, and maneuverability.

A square-shaped hull increase resistance and reduce efficiency. Implementing faired (smoothly contoured) bow and stern sections can reduce drag and improve overall performance.

Additionally, optimizing the hull form, particularly the bow design, can minimize wave resistance, further enhancing efficiency.

Therefore, redesigning the platform's hull to include faired bow and stern elements is advisable to achieve better hydrodynamic performance.

It is recommended to use hulls with autonomous propulsion, which could also be of a hybrid diesel-electric type, even for modular dismantlable configurations that can be deployed in water bodies accessible only via truck transport.

The dimensions of the deck, and consequently of the hull, should have a width of at least 10 meters and a length of almost 30 m and possess the stability characteristics necessary to accommodate the robotic system, allowing it to operate on the side or towards the bow.

One of the operational limitations of the platform used for testing was its central operational basin with four internal guide cable columns and a surrounding hull.

This design prevented the robotic platform from reaching areas of the seabed beneath the hull, significantly limiting potential commercial operations where unrestricted access is essential.

Integrating antennas of varying heights, equipped with cable drums capable of accommodating longer lengths of stainless-steel wire, into a structural grid enhances operational flexibility and efficiency.

Key Considerations:

- **Structural Grid Integration:** Incorporating a robust structural grid provides a stable foundation for mounting antennas and cable drums, ensuring durability and ease of maintenance.
- **Cable Drum Specifications:** Selecting cable drums designed to handle extended lengths of stainless-steel wire is crucial for operations requiring significant reach. Stainless steel offers excellent corrosion resistance and strength, making it suitable for demanding environments.
- **Antenna Mounting Solutions:** Utilizing appropriate antenna brackets and clamps ensures secure attachment to the structural grid, accommodating various antenna sizes and configurations.

By focusing on these aspects, the system can achieve enhanced performance, adaptability to different operational requirements, and improved longevity in various environmental conditions.

This grid should be capable of retracting off the hull and remaining on the deck during navigation. The grid should also be adaptable for installation on standard flat-deck barges, utilizing structural rails.

Incorporating structural rails allows for flexible and secure attachment of the grid system to various barge configurations, enhancing operational versatility.

Additionally, the use of structural rails can accommodate the integration of various equipment and accessories, ensuring that the platform meets specific operational requirements.

Implementing such adaptable systems can lead to increased efficiency and reduced setup times, particularly in operations where rapid deployment and flexibility are critical.

Therefore, the integration of structural rails is recommended to enhance the adaptability and functionality of the grid system on standard flat-deck barges.

Several upgrades should be implemented to achieve a fully operational system, with distinct approaches depending on the main operational environment:

- A) Inland waters such as lagoons, rivers, and lakes;
- B) Open sea environments, including coastal areas and port facility surroundings.

These differing environments require specific navigation, administrative and operational considerations.

INLAND WATERS

Inland and lagoon waters do not require personnel with seamen's books or marine-certified experience.

The unit operating in inland waters is registered in the Port Inspectorate records, and the intervals for navigation suitability inspections are longer compared to those required for marine and coastal waters, which mandate suitability inspections every two years, including hull inspections.

Inland navigation units do not require onboard spaces dedicated to personnel, such as mess rooms and accommodations, and allow the use of hulls with smaller dimensions and reduced construction heights.

These characteristics result in lower operational costs compared to maritime navigation

Implementing a mooring system equipped with adjustable-length spud poles enhances environmental adaptability, allowing the platform to remain securely moored in various conditions, including calm inland waters with strong currents. This adaptability ensures operational stability and safety, enabling precise positioning and controlled movements by using a single spud pole as a pivot point to maintain position.

Employing a single spud pole as a pivot point facilitates small, controlled movements of the platform without losing position. This technique is particularly useful in confined or dynamic environments, allowing for precise adjustments while maintaining stability.

The ability to securely moor in strong currents ensures that operations can continue safely and efficiently, reducing the risk of drift and enhancing the safety of personnel and equipment.

COASTAL AND MARINE WATERS

Operating a sea-going vessel in coastal waters necessitates a qualified marine crew to ensure safe navigation and efficient operation.

The typical crew composition includes:

- **Master (Captain):** The highest-ranking officer responsible for overall vessel command, navigation, and compliance with maritime regulations.
- **Chief Engineer:** Oversees the engine department, ensuring the proper functioning and maintenance of all mechanical and electrical systems on board.
- **Technicians:** Specialized personnel who operate and maintain the robotic mobile platform and other specialized equipment, ensuring their optimal performance during operations.
- **Deck Crew (Sailors):** Responsible for assisting with navigation, mooring, cargo handling, and general maintenance tasks essential for the vessel's operation.

Operating sea-going vessels for daily routes from port to polluted sea zones incurs significant and ongoing costs. These expenses encompass fuel consumption, crew wages, maintenance, and port fees.

To mitigate these expenses, securing a designated berth in the port for overnight stays is essential.

This arrangement offers several advantages:

- **Reduced Transit Costs:** By minimizing daily travel between the port and operational sites, fuel consumption and associated expenses decrease.
- **Enhanced Crew Efficiency:** A stable overnight location allows the crew to rest adequately, improving productivity during operational hours.
- **Maintenance and Security:** Overnight berthing facilitates routine maintenance and ensures the vessel's security, potentially extending its operational lifespan.

2.7 Conclusions

The Seabed Cleaning Platform was successfully tested in both the lagoon and the open sea coastal environments. The lagoon was a particularly challenging environment given the poor visibility and currents in the lagoon channels. Poor visibility made the removal in the Sacca Fisola area more difficult, and identification of the ML items was time consuming. The cable robot had to rely mostly on bathymetry data collected before the cleaning. Once identified the ML item, though, the time to approach the target was very fast (seconds) and the removal took just a few minutes. Even in these extreme conditions, the Seabed Cleaning Platform managed to clean 63% of the items identified with the multibeam echosounder in the Sacca Fisola area and 75% of the open sea coastal area in the Abandoned Mussel Farm site. The system was demonstrated to be quick and efficient, to be able to operate up to 20 m of depth and to collect items up to 130kg, having a real time control on the deck of all the operations of the cable robot. Although the Seabed Cleaning Platform performed really well, some logistic issues related to the open sea operations could be overcome by upgrading the hull of the platform to improve its navigation properties, speed and maneuverability allowing to reach TRL9.

APPENDIX 1

Final set up of the Seabed Cleaning Platform

The equipment consisted of:

- 1) A modular platform certified for sea going licence

;

Figure 35 - Modular platform : design, modules and final assemblage

- 2) Hydraulic gripper with powerpack and umbilical for the flexible oil hoses.

Figure 36 - Hydraulic gripper with powerpack and umbilical for the flexible oil hoses

- 3) Jet pump with high pressure motive water pump for large debris (up to 140 mm) to be sucked from the seabed through the aspiration telescopic pipe

- 4) Inox 316 Hydraulic piston to position the aspiration pipe close to the sea bed.

- 5) Inverter and external plc unit power box for the integration of gripper, piston and jet pump with the control cabinet of the cable robot.

6) Generator set for the power supply of every equipment on board.

ST technical team guaranteed the safety of the whole equipment and safety of all the team that worked during the set-up and during the cleaning campaigns.

1.1 Gripper and Pump driving

1.1.1 System Overview

The system consists of an immersion **pump** for waste suction, a remote controlled with rotation and clamshell system hydraulic **gripper**, an **hydraulic powerpack unit** for the hydraulic circuit, a manual control **push-button panel**, distributors to manage pressure and flowrate of the oil in the various components and four limit **pressure switches**.

The logic control is implemented by a plc.

1.1.2 Characteristics of the components

Submersible pump for general services :

Brand: TSURUMI PUMP

Model: 100C43.7

Motor: three-phase 4-pole (n = 1410)

Power: 4.59KW

inverter for the motive water of ejector /jet pump:

Brand: DANFOSS

Model: FC-202P30KT

Power: 30 KW

Current @ 400V: 55 A

Distributors (Solenoid valves):

Brand: GALTECH

Model: Q25

Voltage: 12V

Power: 58W

Dimensioni in / Dimensions in: mm (inch)

Caratteristiche tecniche elettromagnete / Electromagnet technical features		
Tipo distributore / Valve type	Q25	Q45
Attacco magnete / Magnet connection	Tipo/Type DIN 43650 (vers. A)	
Tipo protezione / Protection type	IP65	
Classe d'isolamento / Coil insulation class	H	
Tensione di alimentazione / Supply voltage	12V D.C./24V D.C.	
Variazione di tensione max / Maximum voltage tolerance	±10%	
Potenza assorbita / Absorbed power supply	58W	
Rapporto di massimo utilizzo / Maximum utilization ratio	100%	
Caratteristiche tecniche distributore / Directional control valve characteristics		
Portata max / Max. flow	50	60
Pressione max di lavoro / Max. working pressure	275 bar	
Contropressione max sullo scarico / Max. back outlet pressure	25 bar	
Manovra di emergenza o in assenza di corrente / Emergency operation or in case of power failure	A pulsante in spinta / Push type	
Trafilamento max di A e B in T a 100 bar con viscosità 35 mm ² /s / Max. spool leakage of A and B ports to T port at 100 bar with viscosity 35 mm ² /s	5 cm ³ /min	

Pressure switches:

Brand: FOX

Model: K55P

Voltage: 24V

Max current: 5A

1.1.3 Operation Logic

The operating logic was agreed during the meeting on 4/7/22 with the technicians of Tecnia. It was agreed to use the commands made available by the Tecnia control system and to replicate the necessary signals internally with the addition of the consents, the management of the alarms and the limit switches provided.

In response to an alarm command sent by the control system, the panel must have a reset, **independent** from the control system.

The inverter for the oil powerpack should provide fine adjustment of the RPM to be able to precisely set the flow rate of the oil pump (use analogue input 0..10V).

The inverter suction pump is controlled by the control system with a 4/20mA output or by an on-board potentiometer.

The panel has been positioned inside the Tecnia cabin near the control system output connectors.

There are **2 pressure switches** for opening and closing the gripper and **2 pressure switches** for detecting the positions of the pump moved by the hydraulic cylinder (up and down).

The logic of the plc allows compliance with the following 2 handling constraints to avoid collisions between open gripper and extended suction pipe:

- the gripper can only open when the cylinder is completely raised
- the cylinder can only lower when the gripper is completely closed

The logic also stops the bucket movements and avoids concurrent complementary commands (for example opening and closing the bucket or raising and lowering the pump cylinder).

1.1.4 External push-button panel

An external push-button panel is provided for the manual handling of the single operations envisaged by the control system. It will be connected in derivation to the terminal board of the inputs and outputs of the plc and will have the following layout:

1.1.5 Software for the PLC

The operating logic is implemented by a plc Schneider Electric **Zelio Logic** with the following ladder program:

1.1.6 DC power supply

The **24Vdc** control section is powered by a power supply unit of at least 100W with 230Vac input connected to neutral/phase of the 400 V 3F+N+G generator power box.

The maximum expected current is 16 A. The power supply will serve the plc, the signal lights, the pressure switches and the coils of the remote-control switches for the motors, if any.

The coils of the distributors are powered at **12Vdc** by means of a transformer with diode rectifier to have continuous current power supply.

1.1.7 AC power supply

The entire system is powered by a silenced and rmp controlled with frequency stabilization generator on board the platform with a maximum power of 88KW (L1, L2 ,L3, N, PE).